

Advances in the scale-up of microalgae production systems

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Introduction

The most relevant advances in the scale-up of microalgae production systems, especially those based on the use of raceway reactors, are reviewed. They include (i) the knowledge of the biological systems, (ii) the improvement of the design and operation of reactors, (iii) the enhancement of harvesting/processing technologies, and (iv) the implementation of advanced control systems including artificial intelligence-based tools. Concerning the biological systems, the models recently developed provide a complete overview of phenomena taking place, including the influence of culture conditions, the presence of different microorganisms, and the role of parasites (Sánchez Zurano et al., 2021). These models allow to determine the most efficient strategies to optimize their performance as a function of these variables, including the prevention of crashes. Concerning design, the use of computational fluid dynamics allows building units up to 1 ha, while minimizing energy consumption below 5 W/m³, and improving the light utilization efficiency by 25%(Inostroza et al., 2023). In the case of temperature, new heat exchangers designed allow to envisage the opportunity for controlling this variable including in large-scale facilities(Rodríguez-Miranda et al., 2021). The optimization of mass transfer capacity allows for the prevention excess of dissolved oxygen concentrations at the same time optimizing the use of CO₂ for pH control, and allowing the direct capture of CO₂ from the air(Barceló-Villalobos et al., 2022). The use of membranes is a major advance for harvesting/processing. Non-pressure membranes allow to pre-concentrate of the cultures at minimum cost/energy consumption while obtaining cell-free supernatants to be recirculated or for safe disposal, while low-pressure membranes allow to fractionate of the compounds of microalgae biomass without using solvents to achieve sustainable processes with zero emissions (Bilad et al., 2014). However, the most revolutionary improvement is the use of advanced control systems that allow for optimisation of the performance of the cultures/systems as a function of target function and environmental conditions. Low-level control strategies allow for the optimization of resources such as energy, nutrients, water, CO₂, etc(Pawłowski et al., 2018). High-level control strategies based on artificial intelligence are capable of adjusting the operation conditions to optimise the performance of the overall system(Munoz et al., 2022). All these advances have been already demonstrated with examples of those applications being provided.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out using two identical 80 m² raceway reactors, located at the SABANA demo plant in the IFAPA research centre, La Cañada, Almería, Spain (Fig. 1). The raceway photobioreactors comprised a double channel of 40 m in length, a paddlewheel connected to an electric motor to recirculate the culture, and a 0.59 m³ sump where the CO₂/air was injected. The culture's depth was fixed at 15 cm, and the process was carried out in semi-continuous mode with a fixed dilution rate of 0.2 day⁻¹, meaning that every day 20% of the culture was harvested and replaced with fresh medium. Freshwater plus fertilizer was used in one system, while urban wastewater was used as the culture medium in the other raceway. The culture was continuously monitored using a SCADA system and a series of sensors connected to a PLC.

Fig. 1. Image of raceway photobioreactors used during the experiments

Results and discussion

The influence of culture conditions on the performance of the biological system was modelled a new version of the ABACO model was developed. The influence of nutrients (N, P) in both the growth and coefficient yields was included. Moreover, the dynamic of daily variation of culture conditions and its influence on the performance of the biological system was included in the model (Nordio et al., 2023). To evaluate the performance of the biological system in real conditions a new methodology based on pulse response experiments was developed. As shown in (Fig. 2) different air pulses are provided to the reactors then both the mass transfer and oxygen production/consumption rates are measured from the values of dissolved oxygen concentration. Regarding temperature, new approaches for the minimization of adverse effects of inadequate temperature in large-scale raceway reactors are developed to optimize the production capacity. Regarding harvesting, the use of non-pressure membranes allows the preconcentration of microalgae cultures while reducing the energy consumption of processing cost (<0.1 kWh/m³, <2 €/kg). The integration of advanced control strategies allows for ensuring stable operation and reliable production capacity whatever the environmental conditions.

Fig. 2. Daily variation of culture parameters in a raceway reactor and values of mass transfer coefficient and oxygen production/consumption rates determined from these values.

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